

Acoustic wave propagation in (layered) magnetoelastoelectric (composite) materials and influence of gravitational subsystems

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The possibility of the shear-horizontal acoustic wave propagation in the transversely isotropic (6 mm) layered magnetoelastoelectric (composite) materials was first shown in 2007 by Melkumyan [1]. The magnetoelastoelectric materials are also called the piezoelectromagnetics (PEMs) because they possess the piezoelectric, piezomagnetic, and magnetoelastoelectric effects. As a result, the (composite) PEM materials are more suitable for spintronics (the future electronics without free charge carriers) and wireless technologies in comparison with the conventional piezoelectric materials. It was found in book [2] and several further publications that in the transversely isotropic PEMs as many as 20 shear-horizontal surface acoustic waves (SH-SAWs) can propagate. For comparison, conventional piezoelectric (and therefore piezomagnetic) materials can support only propagation of two SH-SAWs. There is single review [3] on the subject concerning the PEMs. It was found that several SH-SAWs can also propagate in cubic PEMs [4]. However, the propagation of acoustic waves means energy transmission between the wave generator and the wave detector. One century ago Einstein has postulated that any kind of energy (and any change in energy) is coupled with gravitation. Therefore, it is necessary to treat extra subsystems such as the gravitational and cogravitational to the mechanical, electrical, and magnetic subsystems. This problem of the wave propagation is significantly more complicated.

My current work is coupled with the development of theoretical backgrounds in the research arena (mechanical, electrical, and gravitational engineering) of the acoustic wave propagation in (composite) materials when the mechanical, electrical, magnetic, gravitational, and cogravitational subsystems are coupled [5, 6]. The successful development of this research direction can lead in the future to creation of propellantless spacecrafts and instantaneous interplanetary (interstellar and even intergalactic) communication [7] that can be readily used by the human civilization.

Keywords: transversely isotropic materials, magnetoelastoelectrics, layered structures, acoustic wave propagation, magnetoelastoelectric effect, gravitational phenomena

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